

Stakeholder Perspectives on Transitioning from Current Dengue Surveillance to One Health Surveillance System in Ahmedabad, India

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Abstract

Background: Dengue fever poses a significant public health challenge in urban India, with traditional surveillance systems facing limitations including underreporting, delayed responses, and fragmented sectoral coordination. One Health Surveillance (OHS) offers an integrated approach by combining human, animal, and environmental health data, yet implementation barriers remain poorly understood at the operational level.

Objective: This study explores stakeholder perspectives on transitioning from conventional dengue surveillance to a One Health-based system in Ahmedabad, focusing on frontline health workers' experiences, challenges, and readiness for integrated surveillance approaches.

Methods: An 8-week pilot qualitative study was conducted using targeted literature review, stakeholder mapping, and semi-structured interviews. Pilot interviews were conducted with four frontline health workers (Medical Officer, Laboratory Technician, ANM, and ASHA worker) at one Urban Primary Health Centre (UPHC) in Ahmedabad to assess current surveillance practices and perceptions of OHS implementation.

Results: Frontline health workers demonstrated limited awareness of One Health concepts. Current dengue surveillance relies heavily on external laboratory facilities, with

samples transported to Community Health Centres for testing. Major barriers identified include severe human resource constraints, inadequate diagnostic infrastructure at primary care level, fragmented reporting systems with overlapping platforms, and lack of operational clarity regarding multi-sectoral collaboration. While the existing system ensures functional reporting through hierarchical coordination, it remains vulnerable to logistical challenges and workforce limitations.

Conclusions: Implementation of One Health surveillance at the primary care level faces substantial operational challenges. Successful transition requires foundational system strengthening including capacity building, human resource augmentation, infrastructure development, streamlined reporting platforms, and clear operational guidelines tailored to primary health care realities.

Keywords: One Health Surveillance, Dengue, Stakeholder Perspectives, Urban India, Ahmedabad, Surveillance, Vector-borne Diseases, Integrated Surveillance, Intersectoral Collaboration, Health Systems Strengthening

1. Introduction

1.1 Dengue Surveillance Challenges: Global and Indian Context

Dengue fever, one of the most significant vector-borne diseases worldwide, is caused by four distinct dengue virus serotypes (DENV-1 to DENV-4) and is primarily transmitted by *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes. The global situation shows a serious increase in disease burden, with 14 million dengue cases and 9,000 deaths recorded in 2024, marking the highest epidemic on record (Haider et al., 2025). Global estimates show approximately 390 million dengue infections occur each year, with 96 million cases showing clinical symptoms (Bhatt et al., 2013). These numbers highlight the failure of current surveillance systems, which mainly rely on detecting cases after they occur rather than predicting and preventing outbreaks.

India faces a significant dengue burden, with transmission patterns closely linked to monsoon seasons. The national surveillance system operates through two main programs: the Integrated Disease Surveillance Program (IDSP) and National Vector Borne Disease Control Program (NVBDCP). (Pilot et al., 2019) systematically examined India's dengue surveillance system and found major weaknesses: heavy dependence on passive case reporting that leads to significant underreporting; insufficient laboratory facilities for diagnosis, especially in rural areas; delayed reporting that prevents timely response; and poor coordination between disease surveillance and mosquito monitoring. These problems are made worse by institutional separation, where health authorities work with little coordination with environmental agencies, veterinary services, and community organizations.

Urban areas in India present complex challenges with varied transmission patterns. Urbanization helps dengue spread through several ways: more mosquito breeding sites due to poor water storage and waste management; high population density that allows rapid virus spread; and economic inequalities that create different levels of risk across neighborhoods. Traditional surveillance systems cannot capture this spatial variation, leading to poor resource use and ineffective interventions.

1.2 Ahmedabad as Study Context

Ahmedabad is Gujarat's largest city with over 8 million inhabitants in the metropolitan area, representing typical dengue surveillance challenges in rapidly growing Indian cities. Recent analysis indicates rapid population growth as the chief contributor towards urban expansion, with the city adding significant populations over the past decades (Chaturvedi et al., 2022). The city's location in western India's dry region creates extreme weather patterns, including heavy monsoons that provide ideal conditions for *Aedes* mosquito breeding. Data confirm Ahmedabad's status as a high-burden area for dengue transmission within Gujarat state.

Recent surveillance data indicate that Ahmedabad district recorded high infection rates, with one study noting that infections were particularly high in Ahmedabad district among the areas studied (Nishita S. et al., 2021). The city's layout includes different types of areas: traditional crowded neighborhoods, modern residential areas, industrial zones, and informal settlements where migrant workers live. This mixed landscape creates different environments with varying dengue transmission risks, requiring surveillance systems that can detect detailed epidemiological patterns.

1.3 One Health and Surveillance Integration

The One Health approach is a collaborative framework that recognizes connections between human health, animal health, and environmental systems. The definition of One Health has evolved over its history, however, the most recent definition provided by the One Health High-Level Expert Panel considers One Health as an integrated and unifying approach which sustainably balances and optimises the health of people, animals and ecosystems (Brown et al., 2024). It recognises that the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants and ecosystems are intrinsically linked while also being interdependent (Brown et al., 2024). This approach requires coordinated work across traditional boundaries, bringing together expertise from human medicine, veterinary science, environmental health, and public health.

One Health principle is particularly important for vector-borne disease control. These diseases develop through complex interactions involving disease sources, mosquito vectors, environmental factors, and human populations. Climate change, urbanization, global trade, and ecosystem changes create changing conditions that affect where vectors live, how pathogens evolve, and transmission intensity- factors that single-sector approaches cannot adequately address. Multifactorial determinants of vector presence, distribution and ability of transmitting diseases demand holistic approaches, such as

One Health, which considers the complexity of eco-biosocial drivers and promotes multisectoral and multistakeholder collaborations (Robbiati et al., 2024).

One Health Surveillance (OHS) puts these principles into practice by systematically combining data from multiple sectors to better understand how diseases spread. For dengue, OHS frameworks typically include five main components: improved disease surveillance with better case detection and reporting; systematic monitoring of mosquito populations and infection rates; environmental monitoring of weather and ecological factors; community-based surveillance that involves local people in case detection; and integrated analysis platforms that combine data from different sectors to support decision-making.

Despite growing policy recognition of One Health principles in India's public health system, actual implementation remains limited. Current institutional structures, resource allocation systems, and governance frameworks create significant barriers to cross-sector collaboration, maintaining dependence on traditional disease-specific surveillance approaches (Asaaga et al., 2021).

1.4 Research Rationale: Stakeholder Perspectives

Moving from conventional disease surveillance to integrated One Health surveillance systems requires major changes in how institutions work together, operational procedures, resource allocation, and cross-organizational collaboration. Many One Health surveillance systems have proven difficult to enforce and sustain, mainly because of the difficulty of implementing and upholding collaborative efforts for surveillance activities across stakeholders with different values, cultures (Bordier et al., 2021).

Stakeholder engagement research provides important insights into whether proposed health system changes are feasible, acceptable, and sustainable. Understanding different stakeholder perspectives helps identify what helps or hinders implementation, assess whether institutions are ready for change, and develop strategic approaches for encouraging multi-sector collaboration. This analysis is crucial for identifying influential actors, resource contributors, and potential champions for system transformation.

However, significant barriers exist to One Health implementation. Funding constraints, conflicting priorities, and institutional silos are barriers that hinder the integration of One Health approaches, while participants identified the lack of supportive policies, conflicting departmental priorities and limited institutional capacities as major barriers that hamper effective cross-sectoral collaboration (Asaaga et al., 2021).

This study sought to generate actionable evidence to guide integrated surveillance system policy development, prioritize cross-sector collaboration capacity building, and inform scalable One Health implementation strategies across urban India. By establishing foundational insights into stakeholder dynamics, this research will directly support future operational studies, evidence-based pilot programs, and targeted policy advocacy initiatives essential for strengthening vector-borne disease surveillance systems in rapidly urbanizing developing nations.

1.5 Motivation

1.5.1 Implementation Challenges in Dengue Surveillance Systems

Current dengue surveillance systems in India face operational limitations that reduce their effectiveness in controlling disease transmission. While responses are often considered timely, they are hindered by underreporting, weak data reliability, absence of private sector reporting, and system fragmentation (Paradkar et al., 2021; Pilot et al., 2019). Key barriers include non-involvement of private healthcare, complicated diagnostics, and fragmented reporting structures. These challenges are especially pronounced in urban areas, where complex transmission patterns demand more advanced surveillance approaches.

Although vector control tools can be effective in principle, their implementation often falls short, and routine dengue prevention is rarely achieved in high-density urban communities (Runge-Ranzinger et al., 2014). Traditional surveillance approaches struggle to address the multifactorial drivers of dengue, leaving gaps in early warning systems, resource allocation, and targeted interventions. Strengthening surveillance requires integrating existing governmental initiatives across geographical and administrative boundaries (Pilot et al., 2020). Addressing these limitations calls for integrated approaches that account for human, animal, and environmental factors influencing transmission.

1.5.2 Stakeholder Perspectives in One Health Implementation

One Health (OH) surveillance systems can help overcome these challenges by integrating data and expertise across sectors. However, their success depends heavily on stakeholder engagement and cross-sector collaboration. While OH interventions have been implemented globally, developing countries face significant barriers to adoption (Yopa et al., 2023). The international community and governmental bodies increasingly call for OH systems to address health hazards involving humans, animals, and the environment (Bordier et al., 2019).

This study addresses a critical gap by exploring stakeholder views on transitioning from conventional dengue surveillance to OH-based systems in urban India. Focusing on Ahmedabad's complex institutional landscape, it aims to generate evidence for feasible strategies, identify barriers and facilitators, and guide targeted approaches for building cross-sector collaboration in OH surveillance.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Design

This qualitative research adopts a multi-component methodology that includes:

- Targeted Literature Review
- Stakeholder Mapping through an Interest-Influence Matrix
- Semi-Structured In-depth Interviews

2.2 Targeted Literature Review

The targeted review enabled focused exploration of relevant published and grey literature to map key stakeholders involved in the transition to One Health Surveillance (OHS) for dengue in urban India.

Information Sources: Literature was sourced from databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, as well as grey literature available on organizational websites such as WHO, NCDC, NVBDCP, ICMR, and Ahmedabad Municipal Corporation.

Search Strategy: Search terms included combinations of "Dengue", "One Health", "Surveillance", "Stakeholder", "Urban India", and "Ahmedabad."

Eligibility Criteria:

- **Inclusion:** Articles, reports, and policy documents that provided information useful for identifying stakeholders in dengue surveillance or One Health implementation in Indian urban contexts.
- **Exclusion:** Studies not relevant to stakeholder identification in dengue/OHS, studies focused only on clinical management, or those outside the Indian context.

Screening Process: Retrieved records were screened by title and abstract, followed by a full-text review to determine their relevance for stakeholder identification.

Outcome: The review produced a list of stakeholders eligible to participate in the present study in Ahmedabad.

2.3 Stakeholder Mapping: Interest-Influence Matrix

Stakeholders were mapped using an Interest-Influence Matrix to assess:

- **Level of Interest:** Stakeholder's engagement or concern toward OHS transition
- **Level of Influence:** Policy or implementation authority in surveillance systems
- **Current Role:** Involvement in dengue control and public health
- **Collaboration Potential:** Capacity and willingness for cross-sectoral partnership
- **Resource Contribution:** Infrastructure, knowledge, funding, or operational support

This matrix helped identify enablers, blockers, and key allies for integrated dengue surveillance in Ahmedabad.

2.4 Semi-Structured In-depth Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with purposely selected stakeholders from health, veterinary, environmental, and community sectors. These interviews provided critical insights into the feasibility and acceptability of adopting a One Health Surveillance model.

Interview Themes:

- Stakeholder roles and responsibilities
- Gaps in current dengue surveillance
- Awareness and perceptions of OHS
- Enablers and barriers to transition
- Inter-sectoral collaboration potential

A semi-structured interview questionnaire was developed incorporating themes from the literature review. The questionnaire is structured across six main sections: Background & Current Role, Current Surveillance System (Strengths and Weaknesses), Intersectoral Coordination, One Health Awareness & Perceptions, Implementation Barriers & Feasibility, and Collaboration & Multi-Sectoral Engagement.

Interviews were carried out either virtually or in-person, were audio-recorded with participant consent, and were transcribed verbatim.

2.5 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was conducted on the interview data to identify common patterns, divergent viewpoints, and actionable insights. Data from the literature review, stakeholder mapping, and interviews were triangulated to develop a roadmap for the implementation of One Health Surveillance in dengue-endemic urban settings like Ahmedabad.

2.6 Study Limitations

This 8-week pilot study establishes feasibility and generates hypotheses for future research. The findings are based on interviews with four frontline health workers at a single UPHC and are not generalizable beyond this site. The Interest-Influence Matrix was developed from literature review and requires validation through primary stakeholder interviews. This preliminary work is designed to inform larger-scale studies and pilot program development.

3. Results

3.1 Stakeholder Mapping Outcomes

The literature review successfully identified and categorized stakeholders across four main sectors relevant to One Health Surveillance implementation in Ahmedabad:

1. Government & Public Health Agencies:

Municipal Health System (AMC):

- **Ahmedabad Municipal Corporation (AMC) Health Department:** Municipal Health Officer (MHO), Assistant Municipal Health Officer
- **AMC Vector Control Division:** Vector Control Officer, Chief Health Inspector
- **AMC Solid Waste Management Department:** Superintendent, Department Head
- **AMC Water Supply Department:** Chief Engineer, Assistant Chief Engineer
- **Gujarat Pollution Control Board (GPCB):** Member Secretary, Environmental Monitoring Officers

State & National Health Bodies:

- **National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC):** Centre for Medical Entomology and Vector Management: Director, Joint Director, Research Officers
- **ICMR-National Institute of Malaria Research (NIMR) Nadiad Field Unit:** Field Station In-charge, Scientist/Research Officers conducting vector-borne disease surveillance in Gujarat (actively working in Ahmedabad, Anand, Gandhinagar districts)

Epidemiology & Surveillance Units:

- **Integrated Disease Surveillance Program (IDSP):** State Surveillance Officer, District Surveillance Officer Ahmedabad
- **National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme (NVBDCP):** State Program Officer Gujarat, District Vector Control Officer Ahmedabad
- **LSTM-based dengue forecasting research projects:** Principal Investigator, Research Scientists developing predictive surveillance tools for Gujarat

2. Veterinary & Environmental Health Stakeholders:

Animal Health Sector:

- **Anand Agricultural University:** College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry: Dean, Professor & Head Department of Veterinary Public Health, Zoonotic disease specialists
- **Department of Animal Husbandry, Gujarat:** Joint Director, Veterinary Public Health Officer, District Veterinary Officers involved in disease surveillance

Environmental Health Experts:

- **Gujarat University Department of Life Sciences:** Professor & Head, Entomology faculty, Environmental science researchers

- **Indian Institute of Public Health Gandhinagar (IIPHG):** Director, Professors specializing in environmental health and surveillance systems focusing on climate change and vector-borne disease modelling
- **Physical Research Laboratory (PRL), Ahmedabad:** Director, Scientists in Climate & Environmental Sciences, Vector ecology researchers

3. Private Sector & Civil Society:

Healthcare Providers:

- **Civil Hospital Ahmedabad:** Medical Superintendent, Laboratory Department Heads, Senior Medical Officers
- **Private hospitals (Apollo, Sterling, Shalby):** Chief Medical Officers, Department Heads (Internal Medicine, Pediatrics), Laboratory Managers
- **Diagnostic laboratories (Metropolis, Dr. Lal PathLabs):** Regional Managers, Territory Managers, Laboratory Directors
- **Vector control agencies:** Operations Managers of major pest control service providers, Project Managers of drone-based mosquito control pilot projects (recently launched in Ahmedabad for dengue/malaria control)

NGOs & Public Health Networks:

- **SEWA:** Director/Coordinator Health Program, Community Health Coordinators working in urban communities involved in dengue surveillance, prevention, and control
- **Local Community-Based Organizations (CBOs):** Program Managers, Field Coordinators, Community health workers in high dengue burden areas

3.2 Interest-Influence Matrix

The stakeholder mapping process utilized an Interest-Influence Matrix framework to categorize stakeholders based on their potential engagement and authority in One Health Surveillance implementation. This strategic tool was developed through the targeted literature review to identify enablers, blockers, and key allies for integrated dengue surveillance in Ahmedabad.

The matrix assessed stakeholders across five dimensions:

- **Interest:** Engagement or concern in OHS transition
- **Influence:** Policy or implementation authority
- **Current Role:** Involvement in dengue control and public health
- **Collaboration Potential:** Capacity for cross-sectoral partnerships
- **Resource Contribution:** Infrastructure, funding, or expertise

Based on these dimensions, stakeholders were categorized into four quadrants:

BLOCKERS (Low Interest, High Influence):

- AMC Water Supply Department: Chief Engineer, Assistant Chief Engineer
- AMC Solid Waste Management: Superintendent, Department Head
- Gujarat Pollution Control Board (GPCB): Member Secretary, Environmental Monitoring Officers
- Major infrastructure/utility decision-makers whose actions critically affect vector habitats

KEY ALLIES (High Interest, High Influence):

- Municipal Health (AMC): Municipal Health Officer, Assistant Municipal Health Officer
- AMC Vector Control Division: Vector Control Officer, Chief Health Inspector
- State/National Surveillance & Program Units: IDSP (State & District Surveillance Officers), NVBDCP (State Program Officer, District Vector Control Officer)
- ICMR-NIMR Field Unit: Field Station In-charge, Scientists/Research Officers
- Major public hospitals
- LSTM-based dengue forecasting Principal Investigators & Research Scientists (actively engaging)

OBSERVERS (Low Interest, Low Influence):

- Private diagnostic laboratories: Metropolis, Dr. Lal PathLabs (Regional Managers, Laboratory Directors)
- Private vector control/pest management firms: Operations Managers
- Specialist research units in indirect role: Physical Research Laboratory (PRL) - climate/environment scientists (valuable for long-term planning but not immediate operational role)

SUPPORTERS (High Interest, Low Influence):

- Community & civil society: SEWA (Director/Coordinator-Health Program)
- Local CBOs: Program Managers, Field Coordinators, community health workers
- Veterinary & animal health academia: Anand Agricultural University-College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry (Dean; Head Department of Veterinary Public Health)

The Interest-Influence Matrix was developed based on the targeted literature review findings. The matrix positioned stakeholders according to their documented roles in existing dengue surveillance and public health systems, their institutional mandates, and their potential contribution to One Health implementation.

3.3 Key Findings from Frontline Health Worker Interviews

The interviews with frontline health workers at the selected Urban Primary Health Centre (UPHC) in Ahmedabad provided useful insights into how dengue surveillance currently functions at the ground level and what opportunities and challenges exist for moving towards a One Health-based surveillance system. Pilot interviews were conducted with a Medical Officer (MO), Laboratory Technician (LT), Auxiliary Nurse Midwife (ANM), and Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) worker to further validate the interview tool and assess current surveillance practices and perceptions of OHS implementation.

3.3.1 Current Dengue Surveillance Workflow and Infrastructure Limitations

The Medical Officer explained that the current dengue surveillance system at the primary care level is largely structured around case detection, referral, and laboratory confirmation. Diagnostic capacity for dengue is not available locally at the UPHC, limiting its role to sample collection and onward referral. As a result, patient samples are

routinely sent to a higher-level Community Health Centre (CHC) for confirmatory testing. The workflow follows a strict time-based system: samples dispatched before 1:00 p.m. are typically tested the same day, with results communicated digitally via WhatsApp by evening, while samples sent later are processed the following day. Although this arrangement ensures continuity in reporting, it also highlights the dependence of peripheral facilities on higher centres for essential diagnostic support. The Medical Officer noted that while the system functions reasonably well under routine conditions, it can still lead to delays in timely case management, particularly during periods of increased caseload.

These operational dynamics were further elaborated by the Laboratory Technician, who described the daily logistics of sample handling and reporting. The technician confirmed that the UPHC has no infrastructure for dengue diagnostics and relies entirely on the CHC laboratory for testing. Samples are transported daily, and results are shared through WhatsApp groups, which has helped streamline communication and reduce turnaround time. When samples are dispatched before the afternoon cut-off, reports are generally received the same day; otherwise, results are available the next day. While this mechanism allows for relatively prompt reporting, it introduces an additional step in the surveillance workflow and increases reliance on external laboratories. The technician emphasized that delays in sample transport or sudden surges in suspected cases can slow down reporting, underscoring the system's vulnerability to basic logistical constraints, especially during outbreak situations.

3.3.2 Human Resource Constraints and Workload Burden

One of the critical issues underscored by the Medical Officer was the challenge of human resource constraints. There is limited staff available at the primary level, which hampers the ability to expand surveillance or incorporate One Health approaches into routine work. The UPHC has limited staff who juggle routine clinical work, surveillance activities, and community programs, leaving little capacity to take on additional responsibilities. With much of the burden of surveillance, diagnostics, and reporting falling on a single Medical Officer and lab technician, this concentration of responsibilities underscores a broader structural issue within India's primary health care system, where surveillance functions are often layered on top of already demanding clinical care duties. The human resource (HR) constraints at the UPHC often act as a bottleneck. According to the MO, while the concept of a One Health Dengue Surveillance System is important and necessary, its practical feasibility would require significant strengthening of human resources, regular capacity building, and a clearly defined mechanism for cross-sectoral coordination. In his view, this scarcity of HR would pose one of the major challenges in transitioning to a more integrated One Health surveillance framework. According to him, for such a system to work effectively, there would need to be a clear strengthening of staff capacity, better-defined roles, and more intersectoral support.

The Laboratory Technician raised serious concerns about unsustainable workload, as they are solely responsible for testing, documentation, and reporting of nearly 30 serum

samples daily, along with other routine lab duties. As the LT explained: *"During monsoon season, samples pile up. If transport is delayed or we get 40-50 samples instead of the usual 30, everything backs up. I'm handling collection, documentation, LMI entry, WhatsApp coordination - all alone. One person cannot manage if cases surge."* - These accounts demonstrate how resource constraints and fragmented workflows may impede the scalability of One Health initiatives. Sample handling and transport during high transmission seasons can become particularly burdensome, especially given the existing workforce limitations. The addition of new software (LMI) adds to the complexity of data management, creating overlapping and parallel reporting systems.

3.3.3 Limited Intersectoral Collaboration

From the perspective of intersectoral collaboration, the Medical Officer noted that structured decision-making largely rests with higher administrative levels. Meetings at the local level are more operational in nature, while key planning, integration, and cross-departmental coordination happen at the municipal or district level. The officer emphasized that while health services play a central role in dengue surveillance, broader One Health collaboration such as with veterinary or environmental sectors remains limited and often reactive, usually mobilized only when there is a surge in cases of zoonotic or vector-borne diseases (like Chandipura virus and leptospirosis).

3.3.4 Lack of One Health Awareness

When asked about their familiarity with the concept of One Health surveillance, all respondents- the Medical Officer, Laboratory Technician, ANM, and ASHA worker admitted limited knowledge. Both the MO and LT confirmed they had limited knowledge of the One Health concept when initially asked. However, when the idea was explained, the MO reflected that while an integrated surveillance approach sounded valuable in theory, the ground realities (such as limited HR capacity), already stretched reporting requirements, and sectoral silos would make it difficult to implement at present. The respondents' limited familiarity with One Health highlighted that, in its current form, questions about expected benefits or implementation barriers assume a level of prior knowledge that frontline respondents may not always have. When asked about One Health, the Medical Officer stated: *"I have heard the term, but we don't work with it in our daily practice. If it means coordinating with veterinary or environment people, we only do that during outbreaks. For routine work, I don't know how it would function."*

3.3.5 Community Health Worker Perspectives

The ANM and ASHA workers described their involvement in dengue surveillance primarily through community awareness activities, identifying suspected cases, and facilitating sample collection during outbreak situations. Both workers emphasized their close connection with community members and their ability to identify health concerns early through household visits and local knowledge. However, they noted that their dengue-related activities are often reactive rather than proactive, mobilized primarily during outbreak periods rather than as part of routine surveillance.

Similar to the MO and LT, both ANM and ASHA workers demonstrated limited awareness of One Health concepts. When the integrated surveillance approach was explained, they recognized potential value in coordinating with environmental and animal health sectors but expressed uncertainty about how such coordination would work practically at their level. The community health workers highlighted challenges including lack of community cooperation in some areas, difficulty in following up on suspected cases, and limited feedback from higher levels about the outcomes of their surveillance activities. They emphasized that additional responsibilities would require adequate training, clear guidelines, and recognition of their existing workload constraints.

3.3.6 Communication and Feedback Gaps

Both ANM and ASHA workers expressed that better communication channels and supportive supervision would be necessary for any enhanced surveillance system to function effectively at the community level. They noted receiving limited feedback about case outcomes and the impact of their surveillance efforts, which affects their motivation and ability to improve performance. As one ASHA worker explained: *"We go house to house during outbreaks, identifying suspected cases and collecting samples. But after that, we don't know what will happen. Were they confirmed dengue? Did the treatment work? Nobody tells us. How can we improve our work if we don't know the results?"* The lack of feedback mechanisms connecting different levels of the health system was identified as a significant gap that would need addressing before any system transition.

3.3.7 Fragmented Reporting Systems

Multiple respondents mentioned the use of various platforms for reporting, including WhatsApp groups and the newer LMI software. This fragmentation creates complexity in data management and workflow, with staff navigating multiple, sometimes overlapping systems. The reliance on informal digital platforms (WhatsApp) to compensate for weak in-house capacity demonstrates both system adaptability and structural vulnerability. The Laboratory Technician specifically mentioned how the addition of new software (LMI) on top of existing communication channels adds to the complexity of data management, with overlapping and parallel reporting systems creating additional burden.

Overall, the findings suggest that while the current dengue surveillance process is functional and ensures timely reporting through hierarchical coordination, it remains highly dependent on higher-level facilities and vulnerable to HR and logistical constraints. More importantly, the respondents' reflections indicate that any shift towards a One Health dengue surveillance system would require not just policy-level advocacy but also considerable investment in local-level capacity building, training, and intersectoral collaboration.

4. Discussion

4.1 Systemic and Operational Challenges

The interview findings highlight systemic and operational challenges that could significantly influence the feasibility of implementing a One Health surveillance system at the primary health care level. The Medical Officer emphasized the difficulty of incorporating additional surveillance responsibilities in the face of constrained human resources. With only limited staff available at the UPHC, much of the burden of surveillance, diagnostics, and reporting falls on a single Medical Officer and a lab technician. This concentration of responsibilities underscores a broader structural issue within India's primary health care system, where surveillance functions are often layered on top of already demanding clinical care duties. Such overextension could compromise the quality of both routine service delivery and new initiatives like One Health.

4.2 Awareness and Capacity Gaps

Another dimension emerging from the interview is the lack of clarity and awareness about One Health itself. The MO's limited knowledge of the approach is not surprising, given that One Health has historically been framed at the policy and academic levels, with minimal trickle-down into routine medical practice. The limited knowledge of the approach across all cadres of frontline workers- from Medical Officers to community health workers- highlights this disconnect between conceptual frameworks and field realities, demonstrating the gap between top-level design and grassroots implementation. Without capacity-building, frontline staff cannot be expected to integrate multi-sectoral surveillance effectively.

The perspectives of ANM and ASHA workers further reinforce this awareness gap across different cadres of health workers. While these community-level workers possess valuable local knowledge and community connections that could be leveraged for integrated surveillance, their lack of familiarity with One Health principles and uncertainty about practical implementation mechanisms represent significant barriers to system transition.

4.3 Infrastructure and Workflow Limitations

The lab technician's perspective further illustrates the operational bottlenecks. Dengue testing, for example, cannot be performed at the UPHC due to infrastructural limitations. Samples are sent to the CHC in Faizapur, with results relayed via WhatsApp either on the same day (if sent before 1 pm) or the next day. While this workaround ensures functional reporting, it demonstrates the reliance on external facilities and informal digital platforms to compensate for weak in-house capacity. The addition of new software (LMI) adds to the complexity of data management, creating overlapping and parallel reporting systems. Importantly, the technician also raised concerns about the unsustainable workload, as she is solely responsible for testing, documentation, and reporting of nearly 30 serum samples daily, along with other routine lab duties. The technician's concerns

about unsustainable workload- being solely responsible for testing, documentation, and reporting of nearly 30 serum samples daily, along with other routine lab duties- demonstrate how resource constraints and fragmented workflows may impede the scalability of One Health initiatives.

4.4 Community-Level Implementation Barriers

Community health workers (ANM and ASHA) highlighted unique implementation challenges at the grassroots level. Their reactive rather than proactive engagement in dengue surveillance, limited feedback mechanisms, and lack of community cooperation in some areas reveal gaps in the current surveillance system that would need addressing before One Health integration. Their expressed uncertainty about practical coordination with other sectors, despite recognizing theoretical value, indicates the need for concrete, context-specific operational guidelines rather than abstract frameworks. The community workers' emphasis on needing adequate training, clear guidelines, and recognition of their existing workload constraints before taking on additional responsibilities reflects realistic implementation concerns that must be addressed.

4.5 Main Takeaway Points

When considered together, the narratives from this single-site pilot study point toward major barriers requiring investigation across multiple sites:

1. Human resource limitations across all cadres, with frontline staff already overstretched from medical officers to laboratory technicians to community health workers, making additional surveillance responsibilities unsustainable without workforce augmentation. The concentration of surveillance, diagnostics, and reporting responsibilities on single individuals at the UPHC level demonstrates how workforce scarcity creates bottlenecks that could compromise both routine service delivery and new initiatives.
2. Infrastructural gaps at multiple levels, particularly in diagnostic capacity at lower health facility levels where UPHCs lack in-house testing facilities and must rely on external laboratories. The fragmented digital reporting systems with overlapping platforms (WhatsApp groups and LMI software) create complexity in data management and workflow. Weak feedback mechanisms connecting different levels of the health system further compromise surveillance quality and staff motivation.
3. Awareness and role clarity deficits across the health workforce, where even medical officers are unclear on their role in multi-sectoral systems. Medical officers, laboratory technicians, and community health workers all demonstrated limited knowledge of One Health principles, with the concept remaining distant from everyday medical practice. This knowledge gap extends across all cadres, from facility-based staff to community-level workers.
4. Disconnect between policy frameworks and operational realities, with One Health remaining an abstract concept distant from everyday practice at the primary care level. While respondents recognized theoretical value in integrated approaches

when explained, they consistently emphasized ground realities (limited HR capacity, stretched reporting requirements, sectoral silos) that would make implementation difficult without foundational system strengthening.

5. Limited intersectoral collaboration mechanisms, with coordination restricted primarily to the health sector and reactive engagement with other sectors (veterinary, environmental) only during outbreak situations of zoonotic or vector-borne diseases (like Chandipura virus and leptospirosis). Decision-making and cross-departmental coordination occur at municipal or district levels rather than at the primary care operational level.

Whether these barriers reflect systemic issues across Ahmedabad's UPHCs or site-specific constraints unique to this facility requires investigation at additional primary care sites with varied characteristics.

These barriers align with broader literature on the challenges of operationalizing One Health in low- and middle-income country settings, where ambitious frameworks often falter in the absence of enabling conditions at the grassroots.

Overall, the findings suggest that while the current dengue surveillance process is functional and ensures timely reporting through hierarchical coordination, it remains highly dependent on higher-level facilities and vulnerable to HR and logistical constraints. More importantly, the respondents' reflections indicate that any shift towards a One Health dengue surveillance system would require not just policy-level advocacy but also considerable investment in local-level capacity building, training, and intersectoral collaboration.

5. Conclusion and Future Directions

5.1 Conclusion

The pilot interviews at one UPHC reveal that while the idea of an integrated One Health surveillance system is conceptually sound, its implementation at the primary care level may face substantial practical challenges. These preliminary findings require validation across multiple sites and stakeholder groups. Frontline health staff, including both MOs and lab technicians as well as community health workers (ANM and ASHA), face limited human resources, inadequate infrastructure, and fragmented reporting systems. Furthermore, the lack of operational clarity and training around One Health surveillance suggests that the concept is still distant from everyday practice. Unless these structural issues are addressed- human resource strengthening, infrastructure development, capacity building, and clear operational guidelines- One Health risks being perceived as an additional administrative burden rather than a supportive tool for patient care and preventive health.

The study successfully mapped diverse stakeholders across government, veterinary, environmental, private, and civil society sectors in Ahmedabad, establishing a foundation for future engagement. A preliminary Interest-Influence Matrix was developed to categorize stakeholders based on their potential roles in One Health Surveillance implementation. These insights, while limited to one facility, provide valuable direction for scaling this research to additional UPHCs and engaging higher-level stakeholders identified in the Interest-Influence Matrix.

5.2 Future Directions

Future efforts must therefore focus on strengthening foundational systems before integration is attempted. This includes:

1. Capacity Building and Training: Introducing structured training modules for medical officers, lab technicians, and field workers on the principles and operational mechanisms of One Health. This would ensure that frontline staff understand both their role and the broader value of the system. Training should use concrete, locally relevant examples rather than abstract concepts to enhance comprehension and buy-in among frontline staff who currently demonstrate limited awareness of One Health principles. For future rounds of data collection, questions should be reframed or simplified to first establish basic understanding and relevance in the local context, using concrete examples, scenarios, or locally familiar activities to help respondents connect abstract concepts to their practical experiences.

2. Human Resource Augmentation: Addressing staffing shortages through additional recruitment, redistribution of tasks, or incorporation of mid-level health providers. Task-shifting strategies could be explored to ensure surveillance responsibilities are not solely dependent on already overburdened cadres across medical officers, laboratory technicians, and community health workers. The concentration of responsibilities on single individuals at facility level must be addressed to prevent compromise of both routine service delivery and surveillance quality.

3. Infrastructure Development: Strengthening diagnostic capacity at the UPHC level to reduce reliance on higher facilities for basic testing such as dengue. This would eliminate the current dependency on external laboratories that creates delays and workflow vulnerabilities. Parallel investment in IT infrastructure, including streamlined reporting platforms, is essential to prevent fragmentation and redundancy. Integration of existing systems (such as WhatsApp and LMI) rather than creating parallel reporting mechanisms should be prioritized to reduce the complexity of data management workflows.

4. System Integration and Policy Support: Ensuring that One Health surveillance is embedded into existing structures like IHIP, rather than creating parallel systems. Policy frameworks must translate into concrete operational guidelines tailored to primary health care realities, with clear role definitions for each cadre of health worker. Mechanisms for cross-sectoral coordination need to be clearly defined and operationalized at all levels, not just at municipal or district administrative levels.

5. Pilot Programs with Iterative Feedback: Before full-scale rollout, pilot projects should be conducted with iterative feedback from frontline staff. This would allow identification of context-specific barriers and facilitate adaptive improvements. Community health workers (ANM and ASHA) should be meaningfully engaged in pilot design given their proximity to populations and local knowledge, ensuring that their concerns about workload, training needs, and practical coordination mechanisms are addressed.

6. Strengthening Communication and Feedback Mechanisms: Establishing robust feedback loops between community health workers, primary health centers, and higher administrative levels to improve surveillance quality and staff motivation. Clear communication protocols should replace fragmented systems. Both ANM and ASHA workers emphasized the need for better feedback about case outcomes and the impact of their surveillance efforts, which would enhance motivation and performance improvement.

7. Continued Stakeholder Engagement: Completion of interviews across all identified stakeholder groups to develop a comprehensive Interest-Influence Matrix. This will enable identification of champions, potential collaborators, and entry points for cross-sectoral partnerships essential for One Health implementation. The preliminary matrix developed from literature review requires validation through primary data collection to accurately assess expressed interest levels and demonstrated influence capacity.

By establishing foundational insights into stakeholder dynamics, this research will directly support future operational studies, evidence-based pilot programs, and targeted policy advocacy initiatives essential for strengthening vector-borne disease surveillance systems in rapidly urbanizing developing nations.

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